

INTERLAMINAR DAMAGE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES USING ROBUST INTERFACE ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

For the development of robust interface elements a hybrid mixed formulation based on the potential by Hu-Washizu is applied to overcome the requirement of very fine meshes, due to high stress gradients in the delamination process zone. Additionally, potential and non-potential based cohesive laws are investigated yielding a precise illustration of the single- and mixed-mode behavior. Numerical examples demonstrate the applicability and influence of mesh discretization and the pressure behavior under mixed mode loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

Delamination is a commonly observed failure mode in composite materials. Due to stiffness changes and the lack of reinforcement in thickness direction, delamination already occurs by low loads and can yield total structural collapse. Therefore, interface elements are used for instance to simulate thin resin layers between lamina, providing the opportunity of an adequate simulation of crack initiation and propagation.

There are two major challenges concerning the development of robust interface elements. First, one has to overcome the requirement of very fine meshes, due to the rigid behavior of the displacement based interface formulation. High stress gradient in the delamination process zone results in associated partial bonding in one element. For this reason the element length orthogonal to the delamination direction (l_{elmt}) is defined by the interface elements and not by the adjacent shell elements.

Figure 1: Normal stress distribution in the interface region (a). Length of cohesive zone of a UD IM7/8552 composite with required interface elements inner the cohesive zone (b).

In Figure 1 it is shown, that the mesh discretization of interface elements is the critical value to capture the stress distribution correctly. 2-3 elements within the cohesive zone are at least necessary to determine the stress distribution nearly accurate and get a converged finite element solution. In literature mixed

methods are mainly used for the finite element formulation of plate and shell elements, see e.g. [1, 2]. Herein, additional degrees of freedom are used to reduce the rigid behavior of linear finite elements in numerical applications [3]. As a consequence, the results of geometrical and material nonlinear investigations show an enhanced performance by contrast with purely displacement based finite element formulations. Due to independent and discontinuous shape functions for stresses and strains, the interface formulation can be charged with high-order polynomials which can reproduce the occurring stress distribution quite accurate. The integration order have also a weighty part in the correct modeling of debonding problems with interface elements. The second major challenge is the correct illustration of Single- and Mixed-Mode behavior in simple and more complex numerical delamination problems. A rough distinction is made between potential [4] and non-potential [5] based cohesive laws. In the upcoming numerical examples should show the applicability under pure Mode-I, Mode-II and Mixed-Mode loading.

2 ROBUST FINITE-ELEMENT INTERFACE FORMULATION

Figure 2: Discontinuous interface element in reference and current configuration

The discontinuous interface element is divided into two surfaces. In the reference configuration, the two layers have the same coordinates leading to a 2D configuration which is essential for numerical integration in finite element analysis. For the isoparametric concept the geometry

$$\mathbf{X}_l^+ = \sum_{I=5}^8 N_I \mathbf{X}_I \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{X}_l^- = \sum_{I=1}^4 N_I \mathbf{X}_I \quad (1)$$

as well as the displacements are interpolated with the same shape functions.

$$\mathbf{u}_l^+ = \sum_{I=5}^8 N_I \mathbf{v}_I \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{u}_l^- = \sum_{I=1}^4 N_I \mathbf{v}_I \quad (2)$$

In the deformed state the relative displacements are identified by the vector $[[\mathbf{u}]]$ characterizing the distance between the top and the bottom layer

$$[[\mathbf{u}]]_l = \mathbf{u}_l^+ - \mathbf{u}_l^- = \sum_{I=1}^8 \mathbf{B}_I \mathbf{v}_I \quad (3)$$

with the operator-matrix $\mathbf{B}_I = j N_I$ and the internal variable j which equals -1 for the bottom layer and +1 for the top layer.

$$j = \begin{cases} -1 & \leftarrow 1 \leq I \leq 4 \\ 1 & \leftarrow 5 \leq I \leq 8 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The separation $[[\mathbf{u}]]$ can be interpreted as the strain-like magnitude $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and the interlaminar tractions $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ as the stress-like magnitude, which are related to the separations via a cohesive model. Below, we distinguish a potential based cohesive law by Xu & Needleman [4] and a modified non-potential based cohesive law based on the work of Van den Bosch [5].

2.1 Potential and non-potential mixed-mode cohesive zone models

The most commonly used potential based cohesive law was published 1993 by Xu & Needleman (XN). The potential energy $\psi(\Delta_n, \Delta_s)$ is given by

$$\psi(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) = G_n + G_n \cdot e^{-\frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}} \left[\left(1 - r + \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}\right) \frac{1 - q}{r - 1} - \left(q + \frac{r - q}{r - 1} \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}\right) e^{-\frac{\Delta_s^2}{\delta_s^2}} \right] \quad (5)$$

depending on the normal- and shear separation (Δ_n, Δ_s). Thus, the shape and therefore the behavior of the mixed mode cohesive law depends on the critical energy release rate G_n , the critical tractions σ_{cn} and σ_{cs} as well as the internal variables

$$q = \frac{G_s}{G_n} \quad \text{and} \quad r = \frac{\Delta_n^*}{\delta_n} \quad (6)$$

Δ_n^* is introduced as the normal separation Δ_n at complete shear separation Δ_s and q as the ratio between the critical normal and shear energy release rate. The separation at crack initiation is given by

$$\delta_n = \frac{G_n}{\sigma_{cn} e} \quad \text{and} \quad \delta_s = \frac{G_s}{\sigma_{cs} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} e} \quad (7)$$

Partial derivatives of the potential energy with respect to Δ_n and Δ_s leads to the cohesive tractions.

$$\sigma_n(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \Delta_n} = \frac{G_n}{\delta_n} e^{-\frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}} \left[\frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n} \cdot e^{-\frac{\Delta_s^2}{\delta_s^2}} + \frac{1 - q}{r - 1} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta_s^2}{\delta_s^2}}\right) \left(r - \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}\right) \right] \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_s(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \Delta_s} = 2 \frac{G_n}{\delta_s^2} \Delta_s \left[q + \frac{r - q}{r - 1} \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n} \right] e^{-\frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}} e^{-\frac{\Delta_s^2}{\delta_s^2}} \quad (9)$$

The model provides an efficient tool for the simulation of arbitrary mixed mode delamination problems based on a potential energy function without the knowledge of the present mixed mode ratio. However, regarding Figure 3 (a) and (b), potential based cohesive laws are not path dependent. After complete separation in shear direction Δ_s , and separation in normal direction Δ_n , unphysical negative and positive normal residual tractions, respectively are generated. Detailed investigations about the path dependency are conducted by several authors, e.g. [5] et al., and shall not be considered within this work. A further drawback of potential but also some non-potential based cohesive laws is the unphysical traction-separation behavior under compression.

Figure 3: Interlaminar tractions by Xu & Needleman (XN). Normal traction ($q > 0, r = 0$) (a); Normal traction ($q < 0, r = 0$) (b); Shear traction ($q > 0, q < 0, r = 0$) (c)

The compression region is highlighted as the grey shaded area in Figure 1. In a high compression level repulsive shear and normal tractions are calculated. Comparing the compression area in Figure 1 (a) and

(b) with the one of Figure 1 (c), it can be stated that the miscalculation of normal tractions already occurs for a lower compression level. In many publications high compression levels caused such unphysical traction-separation behavior are considered as irrelevant for delamination simulations on composite materials due to their high initial stiffness. However, in further investigations numerical examples are demonstrating the influence of normal repulsive tractions on the results of delamination analysis. For a robust interface formulation the mentioned drawbacks have to be overcome.

We introduce a modified mixed-mode cohesive law (MODCL) based on the non-potential approach by Van den Bosch [5]. Due to the non-existent potential function, path dependency is present. For this reason we can define the interlaminar traction-separation behavior directly with the Macaulay brackets ($\langle x \rangle = x$ for $x > 0$; $\langle x \rangle = 0$ for $x < 0$) for normal and shear traction under normal tension.

$$\sigma_n^t(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) = \frac{G_n}{\delta_n^2} \langle \Delta_n \rangle e^{-\frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}} e^{-\frac{\Delta_s^2}{\delta_s^2}} \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_s^t(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) = \frac{2G_s}{\delta_s^2} \left(1 + \frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n} \right) \frac{\langle \Delta_n \rangle}{\Delta_n} \Delta_s e^{-\frac{\Delta_n}{\delta_n}} e^{-\frac{\Delta_s^2}{\delta_s^2}} \quad (11)$$

Further, to prevent the unphysical behavior under compression the corresponding relation is extended by a pressure term σ^c . The total interlaminar tractions are given by

$$\sigma_n(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) = \sigma_n^t(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) + \sigma_n^c(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) \quad (12)$$

$$\sigma_s(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) = \sigma_s^t(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) + \sigma_s^c(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) \quad (13)$$

Besides an accurate mapping of the softening properties, the cohesive zone model has to guarantee that the initial stiffness is sufficiently so that the possible separation prior failure is negligible. Furthermore, from a numerical point of view stiffness jumps due to kinks in the traction-separation relation shall be avoided. In order to describe the normal traction-separation relation under compression adequately σ_n^c is chosen as follows.

$$\sigma_n^c(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) = - \left[\frac{\partial \sigma_n^t(0, 0)}{\partial \Delta_n} \right]_{\Delta_s=0} \langle -\Delta_n \rangle = -2 \frac{G_n}{\delta_n^2} \langle -\Delta_n \rangle \quad (14)$$

Hence, the traction under pressure is independent of the shear separation and generates a physical solution. Figure 4 (a) illustrates the normal traction-separation relation for tension and compression defined separately.

Figure 4: Modified Cohesive Law (MODCL): Normal- (a) and shear- (b) traction-separation relation

As a result of increasing normal compression the shear tractions defined by Xu & Needleman reduce (see Figure 3 (c)). From a physical point of view, it is more conceivable that the shear tractions due to shear separation increase or at least stay constant due to increasing normal compression. We postulate a shear tractions σ_s^c exclusively dependent on normal pressure (see Figure 4 (b)).

$$\sigma_s^c(\Delta_n, \Delta_s) = \frac{\langle -\Delta_n \rangle}{\Delta_n} [\sigma_s(\Delta_n, \Delta_s)]_{\Delta_n=0} \quad (15)$$

2.2 Mixed hybrid Interface-Formulation

The variation of the Hu-Washizu functional is enhanced by two additional terms, if compared to a standard displacement based formulation.

$$\delta \Pi_{if}^e(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \int_{\Omega} \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_g^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_g - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_p - \boldsymbol{\sigma}) dV - \delta \Pi_{ext} \quad (16)$$

In addition to the well-known degrees of freedom for the displacement \mathbf{u} , there are two independent field variables for strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and stresses $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, interpolated as follows.

$$\mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{N} \mathbf{v} \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{23} \\ \varepsilon_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{N}_\varepsilon \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{23} \\ \sigma_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{N}_\sigma \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (17)$$

The geometrical strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_g = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{v}$ arising from the kinematics have to be interpreted as the separation $[[\mathbf{u}]] = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{v}$, given in equation (3). Further the physical stresses $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_p$ resulting from the material law are interpreted as the interlaminar tractions. The continuity assumptions for the free variables are supposed to be given by

$$\mathbf{u} \rightarrow C^0 \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rightarrow C^{-1} \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \rightarrow C^{-1} \quad (18)$$

After discretization the first variation is given as below. By substituting the matrices for \mathbf{G}^T , \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{F}^T

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \Pi_{if}^e &= \delta \mathbf{v}^T \overbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{N}_\sigma d\Omega}^{\mathbf{G}^T} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} + \delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^T \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_\sigma^T \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_g d\Omega \\ &- \delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^T \overbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_\sigma^T \mathbf{N}_\varepsilon d\Omega}^{\mathbf{F}^T} \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^T \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_\varepsilon^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}_p d\Omega - \delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^T \overbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_\varepsilon^T \mathbf{N}_\sigma d\Omega}^{\mathbf{F}} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

we obtain the residual vector \mathbf{r}_{if}^e on element level, given in matrix notation.

$$\delta \Pi_{if}^e = \begin{bmatrix} \delta \mathbf{v}^T & \delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^T & \delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^T \end{bmatrix} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{G}^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \\ \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_\sigma^T \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_g - \mathbf{F}^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} d\Omega \\ \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_\varepsilon^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}_p - \mathbf{F} \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} d\Omega \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{r}_{if}^e} \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{r}_{if}^e = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}^e \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

In order to apply a solution technique of Newton's type a linearization of equation (18) is required.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \delta \Pi_{if}^e &= \delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^T \overbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_\sigma^T \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_g d\Omega}^{\mathbf{G}} \Delta \mathbf{v} - \delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^T \overbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_\sigma^T \mathbf{N}_\varepsilon d\Omega}^{\mathbf{F}^T} \Delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \\ &+ \delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^T \overbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_\varepsilon^T \mathbf{C} \mathbf{N}_\varepsilon d\Omega}^{\mathbf{H}} \Delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^T \overbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_\varepsilon^T \mathbf{N}_\sigma d\Omega}^{\mathbf{F}} \Delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \\ &+ \delta \mathbf{v}^T \overbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{N}_\sigma d\Omega}^{\mathbf{G}^T} \Delta \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

This results in the tangent stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}_{if,T}^e$ on element level in matrix notation.

$$\Delta\delta\Pi_{if}^e = \begin{bmatrix} \delta\mathbf{v}^T & \delta\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^T & \delta\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^T \end{bmatrix} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{G}^T & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{G} & \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{F}^T \\ \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{F} & \mathbf{H} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{K}_{if,T}^e} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\mathbf{v} \\ \Delta\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \\ \Delta\hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

By means of a static condensation the free strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and stresses $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ are eliminated on element level. Thereby the stiffness matrix is reduced and difficulties in choosing the correct boundary conditions are avoided.

2.3 Adapted Shape Functions

Below, advantage is taken of the significant characteristics of a mixed finite element formulation. The independent traction and separation fields are enhanced by high order interpolation functions to capture high stress gradients in the slender cohesive zone. In general all variables are approximated by bi-linear shape functions, whereas the displacements are related to the element nodes.

$$\mathbf{u} = \sum_{I=1}^{nel} N_I \mathbf{v}_I \quad \text{with} \quad N_I = \frac{1}{4}(1 + \xi_I \xi)(1 + \eta_I \eta) \quad (23)$$

Simulations have shown that an interface formulation based on a three-field functional with bi-linear shape functions for the displacements, the free stresses and the free strains has no influence on the results, thus the robustness could not be improved. Consequently, to capture the total stress distribution over one element accurately special shape functions are developed.

We determine the occurring stress and strain distributions by solving a Mode-I delamination problem (Double-Cantilever-Beam-Test) using standard displacement based Interface- and Brick-Elements, respectively.

Figure 5: Normalized stress distributions, occurring at the crack tip under Mode-I delamination.

To implement the stress and strain distributions in the isoparametric finite element concept, the results are normalized and described mathematically. With an appropriate rational and exponential approach the numerical values are fitted by the least squares method as given in equation (24) and (25).

$$f_{\sigma_{zz}}(\xi) = \frac{-272.13 \cdot (\xi + 1)^4 + 93.88 \cdot (\xi + 1)^3}{3601.79 \cdot (\xi + 1)^7 - 3.21 \cdot (\xi + 1) + 1} \quad (24)$$

$$f_{\sigma_{xz}, \sigma_{yz}}(\xi) = 0.98 \cdot e^{-9.57 \cdot (\xi - 0.08)^2} \quad (25)$$

By now the free element degrees of freedom $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ are interpolated by enhanced rational and exponential shape function \mathbf{N}_σ^R and \mathbf{N}_ε^R .

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{N}_\sigma^R \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{N}_\varepsilon^R \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \quad (26)$$

The shape functions are given as follows in the matrix notation

$$\mathbf{N}_{\sigma,\varepsilon}^R = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \phi_{xz} & 0 & 0 & \psi_{xz} & 0 & 0 & \phi_{xz}\psi_{xz} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \phi_{yz} & 0 & 0 & \psi_{yz} & 0 & 0 & \phi_{yz}\psi_{yz} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \phi_{zz} & 0 & 0 & \psi_{zz} & 0 & 0 & \phi_{zz}\psi_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

with the following substitutions.

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{xz} &\equiv f_{\sigma_{xz}}(\xi) & \phi_{yz} &\equiv f_{\sigma_{yz}}(\xi) & \phi_{zz} &\equiv f_{\sigma_{zz}}(\xi) \\ \psi_{xz} &\equiv f_{\sigma_{xz}}(\eta) & \psi_{yz} &\equiv f_{\sigma_{yz}}(\eta) & \psi_{zz} &\equiv f_{\sigma_{zz}}(\eta) \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

3 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section numerical examples are presented, indicating the behavior of the mixed interface formulation and the mixed mode cohesive laws presented previously. The unidirectional laminate (UD IM7/8552) is modelled with 4-node shell elements consisting of 24 plies with a thickness of 0.125 mm. The fibers are orientated parallel to the x-coordinate. The resin rich layer is simulated by displacement and mixed interface elements, respectively. The appropriate intra- and interlaminar material properties for all simulations are given in Table 1.

Intralaminar elastic properties	Intralaminar strength properties	Interlaminar properties			
E_1 [N/mm ²]	147300	R_{II}^I [N/mm ²]	2379	σ_n^0 [N/mm ²]	51
E_2 [N/mm ²]	11800	R_{II}^c [N/mm ²]	1365	τ^0 [N/mm ²]	115.7
ν_{12}	0.3	R_{II}^I [N/mm ²]	39	G_{Ic} [N/mm]	0.222
G_{12} [N/mm ²]	6000	R_{\perp}^c [N/mm ²]	170	G_{IIc} [N/mm]	0.687
G_{13} [N/mm ²]	6000	R_{\perp}^I [N/mm ²]	102		
G_{23} [N/mm ²]	6000	$R_{\perp\perp}$ [N/mm ²]	78		

Table 1: Intra- and interlaminar material properties of UD IM7/8552

3.1 Double Cantilever Beam Test

The most commonly used Mode-I delamination experiment is given by the Double-Cantilever-Beam-Test (DCB). The finite element model and the appropriate mesh discretization are depicted in Figure 6

Figure 6: DCB finite element specimen

and Table 2, respectively. The specimen is divided into two regions. The pre-cracked region, without any coupling between the upper and the lower laminate and the interface region, where interface

elements shall simulate the behavior of the resin rich layer. At the other end of load introduction the specimen is fully clamped.

The intention is the determination of the minimal discretization under pure Mode-I delamination, comparing the standard displacement based formulation with the mixed. Due to the simplicity of the pure Mode-I simulation the influence of different cohesive zone models is neglected in this step.

DCB		ENF		SSP	
n^1_{elem}	20	n^1_{elem}	9	n^1_{elem}	16
n^2_{elem}	155-300	n^2_{elem}	28	n^2_{elem}	40
n^3_{elem}	1	n^3_{elem}	14	n^3_{elem}	20
		n^4_{elem}	15		
		n^5_{elem}	1		

Table 2: Mesh discretization for DCB, ENF and SSP specimens

Applying the mixed interface formulation with exponential and rational shape functions (IF-HWZ-GR), the modified cohesive zone model (MODCL) and the gaussian integration of second order, the minimal element length (l_{elmt}) inner the interface region could not be reduced. Below, the integration order is increased to 3. In Figure 7 the load-displacement curves of the displacement (IF-U) and the mixed interface formulation (IF-HWZ-GR) are compared. Applying the gaussian integration of third order, the element length orthogonal to delamination propagation could nearly be doubled ($l_{\text{elmt,IF-U}} = 0.4\text{mm}$, $l_{\text{elmt,IF-HWZ-GR}} = 0.76\text{mm}$). A further increase of the numerical integration order leads to no reduction in mesh size.

Figure 7: DCB: IF-U vs. IF-HWZ (GR), $l_{\text{elmt}} = 0,76\text{mm}$, Gaussian 3

3.2 End Notched Flexure Test

The next simulation refers to the End-Notched-Flexure Test (ENF). The Model is divided into four regions. A pre-cracked region, two interface regions, due to the load introduction in the middle of the specimen and an undamaged region. The finite element model with the applied load and boundary conditions as well as the appropriate discretization are given in Figure 8 and Table 2, respectively.

Figure 8: ENF finite element specimen.

First, the minimal discretization under pure Mode-II loading is determined, comparing the standard displacement with the Hu-Washizu formulation. In Figure 9 (a) we illustrate the load-displacement curve in negative z -direction for an evaluation point in the middle of the specimen. Applying the modified cohesive zone model and the gaussian integration of third and higher order, no further reduction of mesh size can be achieved. Additional calculations on a MMB-Model with a mixed mode ratio of 0.25 show also no influence of the mixed interface formulation on reduction of mesh size. Considering the maximal element length orthogonal to crack propagation under single Mode-II ($l_{elmt} = 0,97mm$) and mixed-Mode ($l_{elmt} = 0,93mm$), it can be seen that it is greater than under pure Mode-I loading ($l_{elmt} = 0,76mm$). Accordingly the maximal element size is determined by means of a DCB-Test.

Figure 9: ENF: IF-U vs. IF-HWZ (GR), min. Diskr. ($l_{elmt} = 0,96$ mm) Gaussian 3 (a);
MODCL vs. XN varying G_t (b)

Further, the influence of the cohesive zone models on the robustness of the finite element formulation, applying the standard displacement based interface formulation, is studied. In chapter 2.1 we already pointed out repulsive normal stresses in the compressive region, which gradients increase for an increasing ratio between G_s and G_n and vanish for $G_s = G_n$.

Below, the ratio $q = G_s/G_n$ is varied by leaving G_n , σ_{cn} and σ_{ct} constant, comparing the cohesive law by Xu & Needleman (XN) with the modified cohesive law (MODCL). For $q=1$ both models are equal. An increasing value of q generates different post peak behavior, depicted in Figure 9 (b). If $q > 2.0$ (note: $q=3.094$ for given interlaminar material parameters) the potential based cohesive law does not yield a converged solution at delamination initiation. Detailed studies have shown that repulsive compressive tractions inner the cohesive zone tending to infinity, depending on the geometry and discretization of the model. Furthermore, the XN-model depends strongly on the load step increment and the discretization tending to no convergence. In contrast, the potential based modified cohesive law shows no restriction for any setting considered.

3.3 Single stiffener panel with ply failure

By means of the single stiffener panel compression test (SSP) we want to validate the achievements received in the two simulations before. The finite element model and the appropriate discretization is given in Figure 9 and Table 1, respectively. The lay-up of the blade is $[(-45, 45)_3/0_6]_s$. It unfolds symmetrically into the skin with the lay-up of $[(-45, 45)_3/0_6]$. At last the skin lay-up given by $[90/-45/+45/0]_s$. Additionally to the interlaminar damage, intralaminar failure adopting the Hashin model [6] is considered. The objective remains to compare the proposed cohesive zone models to the improvement of the robustness using the displacement based interface formulation. The specimen consists of seven regions: Two clamped regions at the opposite site of the specimen, two undamaged regions, two interface regions and a pre-crack region in the middle of the specimen.

Figure 10: SSP specimen with cross section through interface region.

The load-shortening curves are depicted in Figure 11. At a shortening of about 0.6mm, the XN-model shows a divergent solution by contrast with the model by Van den Bosch (VDB) [5] and the modified cohesive law (MODCL). At 0.9mm to 1.1mm axial shortening all models finally start crack propagation.

Figure 11: SSP: MODCL vs. XN vs. VDB with ply failure

Furthermore, the XN-model and VDB-model do not converge after final ply failure. Comparing to this the MODCL-model is a more reliable tool to compute delamination failure, by preventing repulsive normal and shear tractions under compression.

To complete the investigations on the single stiffener panel the minimal discretization within the interface region has to be determined to show the influence of the hybrid mixed interface formulation. At the current state of the research this step is still missing.

4 CONCLUSIONS

With a mixed hybrid interface formulation, based on the potential by Hu-Washizu, we are able to reduce the minimal discretization of the interface region by over 90% for pure Mode-I delamination. We show that for pure Mode-II (ENF-Test) and mixed Mode (MMB-Test) the maximal length of the interface elements (l_{elm}) orthogonal to delamination propagation is greater than under pure Mode-I loading. Therefore the minimal discretization is determined under pure Mode-I. Investigations concerning the applied cohesive law presented by Xu & Needleman, Van den Bosch and the modified cohesive law show that potential and non-potential based models can yield to divergent solution inner the cohesive zone and deserves particular attention. The presented modified cohesive law provides a reliable tool regarding the robustness of simple and more complex delamination analysis.

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